

TITLE

Characteristics of identified natural mentors in the experiences and perceptions of early-and-middle-aged adolescent youth: Implications for formal youth mentoring practice

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ABSTRACT

Natural mentoring is a type of youth-adult relationship distinguished with the supportive and caring qualities. The complex conceptual definition as well as the youth-centred knowledge on this type of relationship in youths' daily experiences are missing in the literature. This empirical article reports the analysis of data subset exploring the experiences of youths in natural mentoring relationships in the Czech context. Overall, 533 young people (aged 11–16, mean age 13.4) in eight secondary schools in the Czech Republic participated in the qualitative open-ended questionnaire, identifying, and describing natural mentors from their social networks. The paper reports results of thematic analysis of selected questionnaire items on young people's experiences and perceptions of their identified natural mentors. Young people identified natural mentors most often (n = 105) among their peers or older friends. Besides, youths mentioned and described grandparents, older siblings, family acquaintances, schoolteachers, youth-group and sport leaders, and one-to-one music teachers as natural mentors.

Identified mentors were most often perceived as 'a good person' with a caring, attentive, empathetic, nice, kind, and friendly nature who, as a result, is perceived as helpful and supportive. Results are discussed with recommendations for further exploration of natural mentoring as a type of youth–adult relationship, naturally occurring in institutions, organisations, and various youth-work settings where youth-adult interactions are part of the service/institution.

KEYWORDS: Adolescents, Sociology of Childhood, Youth mentoring, Natural mentoring relationships, Informal mentoring, Trusted adults, Significant adults, Youth-adult relationships, Intergenerational relationships, Youth intervention

Highlights:

- Analysis of a subset data of 533 young people in the Czech Republic (mean age 13.6 years)
- Youth identified and described their natural mentors in qualitative descriptive questionnaires
- Results describe the characteristics, risks and perceived benefits of natural mentors in youth' perspectives
- Young people identified peers, family members, and formal and informal education teachers and leaders
- Natural mentors were described as 'a good person' with a caring, attentive, kind, and friendly nature

Introduction

A natural mentoring relationship (NMR) is a type of youth–adult relationship that occurs in natural social networks. Traditionally, NMRs are defined as a type of one-to-one, caring, and supportive personal bond formed between a less-experienced, younger mentee and more experienced, usually older adult (Rhodes, 2005). "The term 'natural mentor' refers to a nonparental, caring adult whom a youth identifies in his/her existing social network (e.g., teachers, coaches, adult relatives) (Greeson et al., 2015). This relationship grows into level of significance for the youths as it develops and have a positive impact on youth outcomes in a number of academic, socioemotional, and health related areas (Deutsch et al., 2020). Traditionally, the function of natural mentors is considered as significant in supporting youths during transition to adulthood, strengthening their resilience to environmental and social risks (Philip & Hendry, 1996; Rutter, 1987; Werner & Smith, 2001). Research on natural mentoring focuses on its outcomes, quantitatively measuring health and well-being, socio-emotional development, perceived and received social supports, academic outcomes, vocational functioning, and social mobility (Deutsch et al., 2020; Hagler, 2018; Timpe & Lunkenheimer, 2015; Whitney et al., 2011; Gowdy & Spencer, 2021; Gowdy et al., 2021, 2023). By these parameters, natural mentoring has favourable outcomes of increased resilience towards environmental risks and reduced problem behaviour (Ahrens et al., 2011; Silverthorn, 2005; DuBois et al., 2011; Werner & Smith, 2001); psychological well-being and physical health (Kaufman et al., 2021; Munson & McMillen, 2008); education/work (Timpe & Lunkenheimer, 2015), academic adjustment, persistence, and motivation (Hagler & Rhodes; 2018; Reynolds, 2018), and overall socio-emotional and cognitive development (Van Dam et al., 2019; DuBois & Silverthorn, 2005). Young people with natural mentors were socially more mature and flexible towards traditional gender roles and better able to structure their activities (Werner & Smith, 2001). Their experience of NMRs was associated with decreased depression and suicidal ideation (Ahrens et al., 2011; Rhodes et al., 1994), higher self-esteem (Mirkovic, Brady & Silke, 2024), relatively high satisfaction and subjective well-being together with a high level of physical activity (DuBois & Silverthorn, 2005). Young people showed higher coping and problem-solving skills in relationships (Mirkovic, Brady & Silke, 2024), greater perceived and received social supports (Sánchez et al., 2010), more frequent positive attitudes to education (Zimmerman et al., 2002), and higher probability of graduating from high school and attending college (DuBois & Silverthorn, 2005).

In the U.S. qualitative studies, seven young foster women described a change in attitude towards school, better school performance, improved relationships with family, better ability to cope with emotional issues and handle their feelings, less anxiety, more confidence, and being outgoing in relationships (Greeson & Bowen, 2008). Young people did not fear sharing sensitive personal topics with mentors they would be uncomfortable discussing with parents or other adults (Liang et al., 2008). In a meta-analysis, the presence of natural mentors was significantly associated with positive outcomes for youths' socio-emotional development and academic and vocational functioning, regardless of the youths' risk status, via processes of relatedness, social support, and autonomy support developed in NMRs (Van Dam et al., 2018). Natural mentors are found among adults in the role of teachers, coaches, youth workers, family friends and acquaintances, or neighbours (Van Dam et al., 2019; DuBois & Silverthorn, 2005; Zimmerman, 2002). Regarding the characteristics of identified natural mentors, several studies assessed the qualitative process of NMRs among youths. According to Liang et al., (2008), mentor's engagement and authenticity, and the empowerment that youths experienced during shared fun and enjoyment, were qualities of NMRs perceived by early, middle and older adolescent youths. These features strongly predicted higher self-esteem and a decreased sense of loneliness. Youths valued the support they received in the context of, or enhanced by, the experience of 'fun' in shared activities or during shared trips to the place of activity (Liang et al., 2008). They described features of mutual

trust and fidelity as distinguishing the mentor from other adults, and they valued that the mentor 'kept secrets', was honest with them, and did not lie (Liang et al., 2002:281). Trust that was perceived as mutual by young women in mentoring bonds mediated further benefits of NMRs (Greeson et al., 2010; Greeson & Bowen, 2008).

In Latin American countries of 'Global South', Baker Cervantes & Jimenes (2023) noted and reviewed the research studies written in Spanish on natural mentoring experiences among 'those born into a struggle against the dominance of the Old World, the West, or the Global North' (p. 3388). They argued that most of the current studies on natural mentoring as well as its dominant discourse are centred in the U.S. and Western context. For instance, the U.S. the research recently explored who are the natural mentors by social roles (Johnson & Gastic, 2015), what are the functions of natural mentoring (Miranda-Chan et al., 2016; Monjaras-Gaytan, et al., 2020), qualities of the relationship (Erdem et al., 2016), and the impact of natural mentoring on youth development, thriving, learning and well-being (Hagler and Rhodes, 2018; Kelley & Lee 2018; Miranda-Chen et al., 2016). Studies on NMRs also tend to focus on participants from the targeted groups of disadvantaged youths, such as youths of colour (Hurd et al., 2013; Hurd & Sellers, 2013), youths with experience of foster care (Thomson & Greeson, 2017; Thomson et al., 2016; Gowdy and Hogan, 2021; Greeson & Bowen, 2008), or youths from ethnic (Garcia-Murillo et al., 2023) or LGBTQ+ minorities (Reed at al., 2019; Johnson & Gastic, 2015).

In the European context, Mirkovic, Brady & Silke (2024) analysed a representative data subset of 6126 youth (17-18 years) survey answers collected in the national study Growing Up in Ireland with statistically-representative sample of youth. They compared selected data on the questionnaire item regarding the social supports received from parents or/and other adults. And concluded that youth with the extra-familial supportive adult perceived as available social support showed better outcomes in using active coping strategies, better self-esteem, and identity resolution. In the Croatian study with qualitative questionnaires, Mirkovic & Merkas (2021) examined kinship status, social role and selected sociodemographic features of identified natural mentors in experiences of middle-aged adolescents (n=277). They also analysed the themes of importance of mentors, situations, and places where youths and mentors meet, and topics that were discussed, including conflicts. The theme of natural mentors was also thematised in exploration of experiences of immigrant youths leaving residential care in Spain (Alcaron & Mirkovic, 2024).

In the Czech context, where the presented study was conducted, the exploration of the early adolescents' experiences with significant, non-parental, very important or trusted adults in general population conducted in youth-centred perspective is practically non-existent to date. Vochocova et al. (2024) applied the youth-centred approach with the critics of childism in the study on the Czech youth activists. Kuzmicova with colleagues (Kuzmicova & Supa, 2024; Kuzmicova et al., 2022) leads comprehensive research on children's experiences of reading employing child-centred arts-based participatory research methods. Besides these, a child-and-youth-centred perspective is not employed in the research in the Czech context yet. In research on the Czech youth, Pysnakova (2010) conducted a sociological explorative study on the Czech 'mainstream' youths and emergent adults (15 – 27 years) and their consumers identity formation. She discussed the adult-centred and deficit discourses on youths prevalent in the Czech media as well as the lack of research on daily

experiences of youth in general population at the time. Macek et al. (2016) tracked predictors of identity development and autonomy in emergent adults transitioning into adulthood, referencing to relationships with significant adults in this age group, without direct reference to natural mentoring. Haring et al. (2022) in the large international sociological study on youth (15-22 years) in the four Visegrad countries⁴ compared family lives, relationships, and attitudes of current Generation Z. Kopecky et al. (2021) turned their attention to the social functions and social risks linked with the usage of mobile phones by children and youth (7-17 years) in the school context. The Czech literature also theoretically discussed the benefits of formal youth mentoring interventions in the context of the young care-leavers (Lazar & Blahova, 2020). (AUTHOR's reference) analysed experiences of mentors and related supportive approaches towards mentees in the Czech formal youth mentoring programme.

Overall, the studies on the topic conducted across cultural and social contexts conceptualise the knowledge on natural mentoring as a type of youth-adult relationship occurring in daily experiences of children, youth, and young adults. At the same time, the 'Western', Anglo-American context remains prevalent in the literature on natural mentoring, focusing mainly on the lives of young adults transitioning to adulthood (18–25 years) and mostly in quantitative studies (c.f. Van Dam et al., 2018).

Monjaras-Gaytan & Sanchez (2023) argued in their review on natural mentoring that more research exploration is needed on how different mentors (familial vs. institutional agents) can influence college students' outcomes; and on processes and dynamics of natural mentoring relationships among underrepresented college students is needed. Knowledge of NMRs among the general population of young adolescents (12–15 years) in the EU context, addressed from a youth-centred perspective has not been a strong subject of research to date. Despite the age of early adolescence includes the experiences of extra-familial relationships as a developmental theme (c.f. Coleman, 1969; Vygotsky, 1978; Cooper & Ayers-Lopez, 1985; Colins, 1997; Giordano, 2003; Liang et al., 2008), there are significant gaps in knowledge on experiences of young people of early-and-middle-adolescence age with their natural mentors, explored from the young people's perspectives (Liang et al., 2008). Similarly, the research on the youth in the Czech context focuses prevalently on the emergent adults (15-29 years) and employs the large sociological statistical designs. No studies to date inquired young people's experiences with their identified natural mentors in the Czech literature. Czech studies that would employ the youth-centred perspective are scarce.

Overall, the perceptions of current secondary-school youths in the EU on who their natural mentors are; with insight in their experiences of mentors' characteristics can illuminate the theme of natural mentoring from this novel perspective. Research on natural mentoring becomes significant with the new emergent approaches in formal mentoring interventions that currently acknowledge the significance of natural mentoring relationships in youths' lives. By identifying, addressing, and enhancing the functions of natural mentoring relationships in regular youth-adult interaction, the new youth mentoring interventions can employ the youth-initiated mentoring (Spencer et al., 2019, 2016), network-engaged mentoring (Schwartz & Rhodes, 2016) or intentional

⁴ Visegrad countries include the Czech Republic, Slovakia, Poland and Hungary.

mentoring (Schwartz & Rhodes, 2016) approaches. Knowledge on natural mentoring in experiences of current youth can further support young people while informing new approaches of formal youth mentoring interventions.

This paper addresses the identified gaps in the field to support new youth mentoring approaches in interventions by asking: Who did young people identify as natural mentors in their social networks? What are the significant characteristics of identified natural mentors in young people's experiences and perceptions? What are the benefits for youths of those characteristics in mentors?

Methodology, design, and research methods

This empirical article reports results of analysis conducted on a subset of data collected from 533 youth with qualitative open-ended questionnaires in the extensive H2020-MSCA-ST-IF-2020 study no. 101027291 ENCOUNTER, which explored the experiences of youths in natural mentoring relationships. The research design combined qualitative and quantitative research elements within the participatory research methodology. Methodology was designed in a qualitative interpretive framework (Creswell, 2014) with youth-centred approach and intention to actively involve youth participants in the research exploration. Research was thus designed with intention to give young people the time, space and voice to actively share their experiences and perspectives (Lundy, 2007) on the research theme.

Research sample

Obilor & Isaac (2023) argued that while purposive sampling selects sample members from well-defined criteria based on researcher's expertise and knowledge, convenience sampling chooses its sample members based on proximity to the researcher. The convenience sampling method is used when the target population is small and easily accessible. Purposive sampling technique, on the other hand, should be used when the study focusses on special and sensitive skills, behaviour, attributes, or personalities. Because of the lack of knowledge on natural mentoring in the experiences and perspectives of young people aged 12–15 years in the general population, the study's design targeted the general population of secondary-school pupils in the Czech Republic. According to the sociocultural theories of the development of the self in society^{5, 6} the age range was appropriate for active exploration of the theme of supportive NMRs in youths' lives. As a result, the fieldwork was placed in the Czech secondary schools and the convenient sampling was employed in the sample of respondents:

⁵ e.g. E. Erickson on the identity developmental stage between 12-18 years, c.f. Bishop, 2013; G.H. Mead and his concept of 'Generalised other' in Dodds et al., 1997, or Vygotsky, (1978) and his theory of Mediated learning experience.

⁶ Detailing the argument of appropriation of the age of 12-15 years in young people for exploration of extra-familial relationships with youth's natural mentors (e.g. significant adults, non-parental adults, trusted adults -as discussed above) is not in the scope of this article. However, if the reader is interested, further theories on this age group and their socio-emotional development, including their relationships with extra-familial important adults are available in:.....

1. About 40 schools across the Czech Republic were informed about the study and asked for participation across the Czech regions: schools in the capital of Prague region; and socio-economically disadvantaged regions in West and North Bohemia and North Moravia-Selzian were invited. These regions were selected based on 1. the proximity of schools to the researcher's baseline, considering the staff and time limitations given by funding, 2. The socio-economically disadvantaged regions were selected for comparison with the capital city region. Out of these, directors of the eight schools answered the call and agreed to take part in the study. As the eight research partner schools selected based on the interest of the school directors, the selection of participating schools corresponds with the convenient sampling method.
2. The secondary classes in each of the 8 partner schools were selected for the research participation conveniently to the school schedules, as decided by the school directors in cooperation with teachers.
3. All young people in the selected secondary-level classes who returned the informant consents, answered the open-ended questionnaires. Overall, the convenience sample of 533 young people between 11-16 years participated. All answers in 533 questionnaires by the selected questionnaire items were part of the analysis reported in this article, including IDK, don't have a mentor and invalid answers. Supplement 7. Table 5 shows how many youths out of 533 could identify their natural mentors in the visited classes. Thus, a convenient sampling method was employed also on the participants level with the dataset analysed in answers from all 533 participants.

The convenient research sample of 533 pupils from eight Czech secondary schools⁷ is not statistically representative, as this criterion was not in the scope of the ENCOUNTER project. The sample, however, displays several quantitative characteristics, described in further details in the attached supplements: Most participants (76.9%, n = 410) were living in the city or suburbs, while 10.7% (n = 57) lived in a small town or village at the time of participation⁸. The young people identified their gender as male (47.7%), female (42%) or Other gender (10.3%). Supplement 2 summarises the convenient research sample of partner schools with the number of participating youths. Supplement 3 shows details of participants' age with the mean of 13.34 years, and gender. Supplements 4 and 5 show participants' place of living and socio-economic background, based on their mother's (Table 4a) and father's (Table 4b) education.

⁷ The convenience sampling method (Obilor & Isaac, 2023) was used in selecting the research partner schools, participating classes and young people who participated in the study. As a result, 533 youth answered the qualitative descriptive questionnaire.

⁸ C.f. Vobecká, J., & Pigué, V. (2011). *Fertility, Natural Growth, and Migration in the Czech Republic: an Urban-Suburban-Rural Gradient Analysis of Long-Term Trends and Recent Reversals*. *Population, Space and Place*, 18(3), 225–240. doi:10.1002/psp.698 PAGES 226-227 for arguments on the urban-rural sub-divisions of the places of living, tracked among the respondents of the study.

Fieldwork design

The ethical approval for the study was received in February 2022, granted by the project's Host institution and its Research Ethics Committee (c.f. Supplement 1 on the REC Certificate). The fieldwork took place in the 8 partner secondary schools in the Czech Republic during Spring 2022-Spring 2023. Following the consent of the 8 research partner schools, the researcher organised three fieldwork visits to the schools. The fieldwork visits were integrated in regular teaching schedule of the participating classes:

1. On the first visit (one class hour, 45 mins.), the researcher introduced and explained the theme and aims of the project, aided by the youth-centred animated video developed for the project's purpose as a participatory youth-centred research method. The theme of natural mentors was subsequently discussed with the class, and questions were addressed. All pupils received informed consent forms developed for youths in a youth-centred mode, and for parents. Youths were asked to bring the forms back in 7 days in the latest. Informant consents informed potential participants about the study ENCOUNTER: the options of research participation were divided into 5 steps and described. The informant consent also contained the option to agree with the data deposition in the data archive according to the FAIR research principles. The participants selected one or more options of participation (c.f. Supplement 10 and Supplement 11 for the Informant consents, attached in the original Czech version).
2. The second visit at the school was organised 1 week after the first visit in the same class. The young people who consented to participate, took part in the qualitative descriptive questionnaire.
3. During this visit, the researcher firstly screened the animated video in the class again.
4. Following the video screening in the classroom, the researcher invited young people to identify and describe their own natural mentors and experiences with them in open-ended questionnaires during the rest of the school class (cca 35 mins), filled in electronic form.

Figure 1: Shows how the fieldwork design was implemented in participants selection and data collection during the fieldwork in the research partner schools

Data collection methods

Identification of the natural mentors in data collection methods differ across studies. Several studies (Harris et al., 2009; Hagler & Rhodes, 2018; Kelley & Lee, 2018; Miranda-Chan et al., 2016; Johnson & Gastic, 2015) approached the exploration of natural mentors with analysis of answers on the question from the U.S. National Longitudinal Study of Adolescent to Adult Health: 'Other than your parents or step-parents, has an adult made an important positive difference in your life at any time since you were 14 year old?' Similarly, Mirkovic, Brady and Silke (2024) analysed a dataset of selective items from the quantitative survey 'Growing up in Ireland' with national youth sample (17-18 years) exploring links with the natural mentors.

Laursen and Birmingham (2003) in the study on foster youth's resilience factors employed in-depth, semi-structured ethnographic interviewing to learn how foster youth ($n = 23$) make sense of the functions of caring adults in their lives. Baker Cervantes & Jimenez (2023, p. 3390) conducted interviews on natural mentoring experiences among youth, alumni and teachers in schools, opened by prompting interviewees: 'To think about adult in their life, other than their parents or guardians, which had made an important positive difference in their life and share one of their most recent favourite memories of this adult.' Mirkovic (2023) approached the theme asking youth (15-18 years) to identify the significant adult in their life and describe their significance. Simmons (2007, p.5) in link to academic natural mentoring concluded that the process of identification of a natural mentor – a person significant for one's career or professional development - can be supported by a question: 'Who has most conveyed inspiration to me for a long haul?' Finally, Koper et al. (2020, p. 7) approached prompt for youth to identify the Youth-Initiated natural mentors (YIM) with more details. They explained who the natural mentors are: 'YIM is someone who is trusted by the youth, someone s/he can go to for support or advice, and/or someone who inspires the youth.' Subsequently, the youth was asked to identify who their YIM could be. If necessary, the YIM intervention professional supported the young person in identifying a potential YIM by selected participatory exercise, e.g. by making a social network map.

Participatory youth-centred animated video: The presented study aimed the research at the youths of the secondary-school-age (11-16, 13.6 in average). As we targeted youths of early adolescence age and followed the current participatory ethics of research with children and youths (Lundy, 2007). We considered the prompt necessary to be 1. Youth-centred, 2. Actively engaging youth into the explored theme. After assessing the current visual arts-based methods with children and youth (Ford & Campbell, 2018; Torre & Murphy, 2015; Epstein et al., 2006), the research theme was approached innovatively with the animated video, designed as a participatory youth-centred arts-based research method. With intention to actively engage youth participants into the research exploration.

The scenario was based on the literature review on the NMRs characteristics published between 2000 – 2020 (see above). The video was designed in youth-friendly communication mode 1. as general explanation of the suggested research theme; 2. as a prompt asking young people to actively identify and describe their own experiences and perceptions of the research theme in their lives. The video was particularly addressing the research question 'Who the natural mentors are in general?' The video is 2:19 minutes long. It's scenario was written in the Czech language and can be summarised as follows:

The mentor is not your parent nor the sister or brother of your age, but it can be somebody close or important to you in your family or outside it. It is someone older and more experienced than you. Someone you like. Someone who supports you if you need. Someone important who you can trust. Someone who helps you if you turn to them. You like to spend time with them, you meet them regularly and enjoy your time together. They can have skills you admire and would like to acquire too. In short, it is your favourite older person around you we'd like to know about more. Could you, please, now identify and describe your own natural mentor?

Open-Ended Qualitative Questionnaire: The qualitative, descriptive, open-ended online questionnaire was developed for the study based on the current literature review in the field and the identified gaps of knowledge (e.g. with items in the youth-friendly language, other gaps see above). The research design of the questionnaire was previously developed and tested in the study on the children's attitudes to scientists with participatory research methods (AUTHOR'S REFERENCE, 2022)⁹. The approach of this instrument was now found viable, with the adjustments made according to the research theme in this study.

The questionnaire contained the animated video, developed for the study, followed by 31 open-ended and 28 closed questions (Supplement 6). After watching the video on general natural mentors, young people were asked if they could identify someone particular in that role within their social networks - and describe them. The themes in items of the questionnaire concerned to youths' personal details; description of identified mentor; youth and mentor in the relationship; last meeting with mentor; other important people in youth's life; youth's personal and family background. This study reports the analysis of the questions about the mentor characteristics and youths' background details.

This article reports the data collected in the selected questionnaire items on identification and description of natural mentors in youth's experiences and perceptions together with the items on the participants' background (c.f. Supplement 6, items marked in bold). The dataset collected by this qualitative, open-ended questionnaire method is valuable for it innovatively engaged youth with active involvement giving space to youth's own language and expressions, and perceptions in mentors' identification and descriptions. The open-ended questions allowed youths to become aware of the natural mentors in their life and describe them in their own perspective while having time to think about experiences with them on their own. This was reflected as a valuable experience from youth in their feedback given on the questionnaire's participation.

⁹ (Author's reference, 2022) similarly used the qualitative open-ended questionnaires in the study that explored perceptions of science and scientists described by Irish pupils. It also aimed to re-focus the traditional survey method in exploration of the topic with youth towards participatory approach with active engagement of youth in exploration of the research theme. Firstly, the prompt 'Please, draw the scientist' was used as the arts-based participatory method with youth engaging with the research theme. Subsequently, the participants were asked to describe their drawings in the open-ended qualitative descriptive questionnaire.

Data analysis

The overall emphasis was put on the qualitative analysis of youth's experiences and perceptions of their identified natural mentors. The collected qualitative questionnaire dataset (n = 533) was analysed with thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006) using QSR NVivo 14 software, with focus on 1. Youth's own descriptions of mentors, 2. Youth's language expressions. These were coded by themes following the thematic analysis of qualitative questionnaires described previously in (AUTHOR'S REFERENCE, 2022). Firstly, the 'word frequency' function firstly revealed the most frequent expressions used in each of the 59 questions. These expressions were grouped with stemmed words (same expression in different grammatical forms) and with synonyms. A Codebook was developed for each question, with thematic categories derived from the frequent synthesised expressions and using the authentic expressions in the name of categories and their descriptions in the youths' answers. In this article, the results of a thematic analysis are presented on the selected questionnaire items addressing the research questions. Results of thematic analysis are reported in the paper under Results 2 and Results 3 sections.

Additionally, the answers on youths' background were analysed in SPSS with descriptive statistics and cross-tabs on the questionnaire items data to gain an insight on the youth's descriptions of their identified mentors and their own background data – such as gender and age of both, young people and identified mentors. Crosstabs and descriptive statistical tests were run in SPSS program with the collected questionnaire data. These are described in this article as Results 1 and in Supplementary tables.

Figure 2: Shows how the Thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006) on perceptions of mentors was integrated with descriptive SPSS tests on the background info.

The results of the study ENCOUNTER, including those reported in this paper, were discussed, and validated with the sub-sample of the study's respondents in the partner school¹⁰. As well as with the professionals from the community of practice in the field of education and youth mentoring social services in the Czech Republic, Slovakia, Netherlands and internationally, via in-person workshops and online webinars. These were dedicated to the study findings' presentation with subsequent discussion on the results with these selected groups.

Limitations

The schools were conveniently selected according to their interest in participating in the ENCOUNTER project. Because of the Ukraine war crisis and the wave of young refugees needing inclusion in Czech schools at the time of fieldwork (spring 2022), this study took place only in the seven schools in Prague and one school in a disadvantaged region. It does not report data of a statistically representative sample of the research participants. Because of time, funding design, and budget and contextual restrictions, this was not an option for this project. Following school, parental and youths' consents, the study was included into the regular teaching hours. Respondents to the qualitative questionnaires were part of the whole selected participating classes. Thus, partial generalisation of the results can be made. Though the schools are not a statistically representative sample of the Czech Republic, they may be somewhat representative of large schools in Prague suburbs.

Nevertheless, the study is valuable for its novel approach and results are significant for the detailed qualitative content scoping the youth perspective on the natural mentoring experience. To achieve representativeness of these results, future research should further explore the same theme among youths with a representative sample of participating schools, especially in socially disadvantaged and rural regions in the Czech Republic and internationally.

The animated video on the research theme used as an introduction and prompt for youths is developed on the arts-based participatory research methods such as Photo Elicitation Interviews (Nelson, 2019; Ford & Campbell, 2018; Epstein et al., 2006). Nelson argued that 'photographs can be provided by the researcher, produced by the participant, or selected by the participant.' Epstein et al. (2006) provided rationale of situations when the photos selected by researchers on the research exploration with children are justified that were also relevant in the case of this study. Harper (2014) conceptualised the process of 'breaking the frame' of the participants normal views while providing pre-selected visual prompts for research exploration. All these arguments were relevant for developing the novel youth-centred animated video for exploration of the theme of the presented study - We employed an animated youth-centred video on the research theme following the current literature review in the field and providing the general information while seeking youths' interpretation of this initial prompt searching for their own experiences and perceptions of the research theme. This approach is novel in the field of youth mentoring, youth-adult relationships, youth-centred research conducted in the Czech context with the active engagement of youth into the research theme.

¹⁰ School 5 of the research sample agreed to participate with its 2 classes in the follow-up research visit. During this visit, the researchers introduced and discussed the research findings with young people who participated in the questionnaires during the fieldwork.

Young people followed the video with identification of their natural mentors – significant adults, important adults and overall, the people that are crucial in their lives – and subsequently provided feedback with positive reflection on exploration of such adults in their lives. They especially positively regarded that they recognised these adults with new awareness while acknowledging their importance and positive influence in their lives. They could feel positively empowered with this recognition given by the time and space they had during their research participation in exploration of the research theme. Thus, the animated video facilitated ‘brake of the frame’ while giving an opportunity to reflect and recognise the theme in participants’ lives that is important to them but not acknowledged consciously in the daily life. Similar feedback described Mirkovic (2023) reflected on youth’s significant and supportive adults in their social networks in Croatia.

Our youth-centred participatory animated video as the novel participatory research tool in participants selection and the data collection with youths, nevertheless, needs to be further tested in the future studies. Using different versions of 1. the video content, 2. Animation, 3. Data collected with the traditional verbal prompt used in the studies on the theme to date, now with the same age group as in this study can validate the method we developed in this study. The data and their analysis should be then compared among different datasets collected using the variations of this novel research tool. While such methodological experiment could not be in the scope of this study, it could validate this novel research method as a valuable research tool for youth-centred research and practice in the field in the future.

Results

This paper reports the results of thematic analysis addressing the research questions: 1. Who did young people (aged 11–16) identify as their natural mentors in their social networks? 2. What characteristics are perceived as significant in the identified natural mentors, and what is their role in young people’s lives? What, in youths’ experiences, are the perceived benefits of natural mentors in the role of role models for youths?

Results 1: Who did young people identify as their natural mentors in their social networks?

Results 1 address the demographic descriptions of the natural mentors identified by young people. These results are reported in four tables on the overall perception of mentors’ presence in young people’s lives, and on their social roles, gender, and age. Overall, 50.1% of youths were able to do so (c.f. Supplement 7). Following that, Table 1 shows the social roles of identified natural mentors in youths’ lives with examples of youths’ descriptions. Most young people (n = 105) considered friends as their natural mentors. Respondents also often identified and described grandparents, schoolteachers, sports coaches, older siblings, leisure-time teachers, extended family members (such as cousins or aunts), or family acquaintances (such as parents’ friends and colleagues) as natural mentors in their lives. Several mentioned people without specifying their roles, or they were unsure if they had any natural mentors. Finally, young people identified their favourite schoolteachers as natural mentors. Interestingly, several identified their parents despite the video explicitly instructing otherwise, which is addressed further in discussion below.

Table 1. Who did young people identify as natural mentors?

Who is identified as natural mentor by youths?	Frequency in total	Frequency by age (in estimated years)						Content
		15-20	21 – 26	27 – 30	31 – 50	50+	IDK their age	
A peer-friend/Older friend/Family acquaintance	105	73	13	3	10	1	5	Identified mentors: their role in youths' lives My best friend; my wiser friend; my friend who is older and we share an interest in horse-riding, my mum's friend; My mum's friend who is a tennis pro; my family's friend
Grandparent	60	0	0	0	0	57	3	My granny; Granddad
Older siblings	25	15	7	3	0	0	0	My older brother; older sister; Brother 10 years older...
Sport coach	39	3	9	5	14	4	4	Breakdance coach, badminton coach, dance teacher, table tennis coach, gym trainer, Tennis coach for kids, golf coach, judo coach; he trains the physical/mental strength
Favourite schoolteacher	43	1	6	7	15	10	4	Music teacher, English teacher, P.E. teacher
Teacher of leisure-time interest/activity: One-to-one teacher or youth group leader	14	0	1	2	2	4	5	Drums teacher; musician/teaches the guitar; violin teacher; teacher of the Airforce leisure group; theatre teacher: Dance teacher, she teaches kids dancing; Teacher in the transport & driving playground; Piano teacher; my English lecturer...
Parents	36	0	0	1	33	2	1	My mum; my dad
Other family member	11	0	0	5	5	0	1	my auntie; my cousin
Man or Woman	53	0	11	8	18	12	4	General man or women without closer details given
Digital/Online person/YouTuber/Public person/Professional	23	3	5	4	5	6	0	Kendal Jenner, favourite YouTuber; Actor; Rapper; football professional; psychologist; influencer; twitch streamer; therapist; professional football player and youtuber – a woman. Cristian Ronaldo; Dancer; Mirek Dusin (a book hero)
IDK/I don't have a mentor/Invalid answer	128							
TOTAL	537							

Legend: Table 1 shows who respondents identified as their natural mentors following the youth-centred animated video on the theme.

Table 2 shows that young people who participated in the study identified their mentors in congruence with their gender: Boys predominantly identified male mentors; girls described female mentors. Similarly, youths who identified as 'Other gender' identified mentors mostly in the same group.

Table 2: Identified gender of the natural mentors in comparison to the self-identified gender of youths

Gender of participant	Gender of identified mentor			IDK	TOTAL
	Male	Female	Other gender		
Boy	140	50	6	58	254
Girl	52	135	2	35	224
Other gender	12	8	15	20	55
TOTAL	204	193	23	113	533

Legend: Table 2 shows that the gender of the identified natural mentors marked in bolt correlated with the gender of young participants

Table 3 describes young people’s perception or estimation of their identified mentors’ age, while linking this with the respondent’s age (11–16 years). It shows that respondents most often perceived their mentors in a) a group of their peers who are very close to their age, and b) a group of adults significantly older than them. In particular, 73 young people identified their friend of the similar age (15-20 years) while 16 youths identified mentors aged between 21-30 years. On the other hand, 11 respondents identified much older friend age between 31 to 50+. The two middle groups for mentor’s age were reported only in several cases. Despite these findings are not statistically representative, they are in congruence with the literature on NMRs and are discussed further below. Further study with the statistically-representative sample of research participants is, however, recommended for the future research to validate these results, significant for the youth mentoring interventions.

		Age of Identified Mentor						TOTAL
		15 - 20	21 - 26	27 - 30	31 - 50	51+	IDK	
Age of participants	11	6	2	3	8	13	9	41
	12	17	7	12	30	26	29	121
	13	33	14	10	20	16	31	124
	14	20	14	8	21	25	34	122
	15	14	14	6	22	22	23	101
	16+	8	3	0	1	3	9	24
	TOTAL	98	54	39	102	105	135	533

Table 3: Age of the Identified Mentor: Legend: Marks in bolt distinguish the most common age of the mentor identified by youths in each age group, excluding I don’t know (IDK) answers.

Results 2: What characteristics of identified natural mentors are perceived as significant in young people's lives, and why?

After analysis of mentors' roles in youths' lives and their gender and age in youths' perceptions and experiences, Results 2 now report youths' perceptions of the most likeable features in identified natural mentors.

Table 4 shows the general characteristics mentioned by youths in descriptions of their identified mentors. Young people commonly described their mentor as a good person who is attentive to them: 'is considerate to others'; 'is a nice person who wouldn't hurt even an enemy'; 'a kind person' they find easy to connect with in a common language. They emphasised a 'friendly' and 'caring' personality. A mentor in relation to youths and others is 'empathetic', 'helpful', 'caring', a 'good listener', 'understanding and trustworthy' – young people can turn to them in trust, as they believe the mentor gives them good advice and support. Identified mentors' kind and supportive nature is recognised and emphasised most often in their personalities. This group of features was perceived in mentors by 35.3% of youths in the questionnaires.

Young people also described mentors' intelligence, wisdom, experience, and honesty, and their responsible and reliable nature and hardworking habits as well as a sense of humour they shared with the identified mentor. These positive characteristics can be inspiring and motivating for youths, as further argued in the analysis below.

Interestingly, youths also mentioned negative characteristics of mentors, such as 'grumpy', 'stubborn', 'impulsive', and 'angry', and mentioned 'a thief' among other characteristics under this theme. These findings are discussed below in relation to the risks of natural mentoring relationships for youths.

Table 4: What are the characteristics of your identified mentor?

Generated most frequent categories	Frequency	%	Subcategories	Content/Category description by youth respondents - examples
Good person with caring, attentive, empathetic, and friendly nature	269	35,3	Nice/Kind/Caring/Friendly	Nice person; kind to other people; sympathetic; couldn't hurt even an enemy; easy to find the common word with; good person; nice and caring; good heart; understanding; considerate; caring; Takes care of others; easy-going; friendly; calm
			Empathetic/Helpful/Supportive	Always listens; helps other people; dedicated to care of others; always helpful; always gives a good advice; supports me; willing to help me; I can trust her and turn to her for advice; attentive to me; I feel good with her; helps me to fulfil my dreams; nice but strict when I play it lazy; calms me down
Funny/Witty/Sense of humour	65	8,5	n/a	Ironic; jolly; can make fun of themselves; sense of humour; makes jokes; makes me laugh.
Clever/Smart/Wise	44	5,8	n/a	Educated and smart; has lots of experience; lots of knowledge
Responsible/Reliable/Hardworking/Inspiring	22	2,9	n/a	Reliable; ambitious; hardworking; handy; works quickly and does things well; has high goals; does his best at work, competitive; talented; inspiring; self-confident; energetic; optimistic.
Honest/Sense of justice/Noble/Courageous	21	2,8	n/a	Fair play, good man, truthful, honest, noble, real, straight; courageous;

Negative characteristics: Unpleasant/Strict/Grumpy/Angry/Moody/Silly	28	3.7	n/a	Angry man; stubborn; aggressive; harsh; impulsive; bad man; can be grumpy; trouble-maker; posh; gets upset quickly; moody; has a desire to extinct people; a steel; depressive; a nuts; silly; lazy, bad tempered
IDK/Don't have a mentor/Invalid answer	207	27,2	n/a	I can't describe it, I don't know, I don't want to tell. I don't have a mentor
Other answer	105	13,78	Physical appearance	Mega tall; green ninja; a beauty; cute; a big guy; strong; short hair; stocky
			Other positive characteristics	Great person; he is a calm guy who dedicates all his free time to his family; autonomous; playful; still a bit of a kid and likes to eat a lot too; always cool; a cool guy; he's a legend; a character; strategic and motivating; sociable; emotional; extroverted; chatty; eat everything; loving; he shouts sometimes but with a good intention.
			Good in selected skills	Cooks very well; plays football; can fly with helicopter; can play tennis; can sing nicely; can do breakdance; knows plants in latinish etc.; best teacher in school, knows history.
			Other answers	Is like me; likes German 😊; a teacher; a chef; a reader; a dog-lover; secret; trader; millionaire; prof. Trading
TOTAL	761		100	

Following the results in Table 4, Table 5 distinguishes the detailed features that young people found most likeable in their mentors and in their experience with them, in three main thematic groups: 1. Features perceived as likeable in mentor's personality, 2. Features perceived as enjoyable in interactions with mentors, 3. Features of resulted benefits of interactions with identified mentors for youth in daily experience. This analysis extends the general descriptions of mentors' characteristics (Table 4) with perceptions of features that are specifically important for youths in mentors because 1. distinguish mentors as individuals in youths' lives and their importance for youths; 2. Identify features valued by youths in the mentoring interactions; and 3. Distinguished subtle features of mentoring benefits in daily lives of youth.

Table 5: What do you like the most about your identified mentor?

Category	No.	%	Subcategories	Content
Support and Empowerment	72	12.9	c. Supports me/Helps me in particular life events	he is always here for me; I can turn to her anytime I don't understand something; he supports me; He helped me in different life situations; she is nice for helping me like no one else; she helps me in coming to terms with different things;
			c. Encourages me/Empowers me/Gives me good advice	By supporting me and telling me that I can do it because I am good in it; he can encourage me; she helps me to make my dreams come true; she spends time with me studying; she explains the exercises for us; he is wise and always gives good advice for my life; he can give a good advice when I turn to him; when I don't know something she either encourages me and navigates me to find the thing on my own or tells me the solution; he never says NO so I can ask anything to him anytime

Care	60	10.8	b.Likes me/ Has time for me/ Cares of me	I know she likes me lot; she takes me for the trips; she has time for me, she likes spending time with me. She cares of me; she brings food and cares of us; she cooks French-fries for me; she is interested in me
			c.I can talk to them/Listens to me	She is willing to talk to me; she likes talking to us and she always listens to me; I like her because I can talk to her; he's my uncle and I like talking about school with him.
Age factor – characteristics in perceived age difference	30	5.4	a.My inspiration in their character and lifestyle	His opinions and lifestyle; long years of studies; his character; his personality; his past (he was a soldier); his routines; his worldview; courage – doesn't give up. He is cool; he's simply a legend; his profession.
			a.My inspiration in their behaviour/skills/their experience and wisdom	he can be my role model; he's got lots of experience he can pass on to me; I like his adventures he experiences with his friends; he can solve the problems calmly; she is talented; creative; strong and can throw things far away; he's a good teacher; he's an amazing musician; he can speak languages; she is very philosophical; he's got great skills in IT.
Fun factor - I feel good with them, I enjoy being with them	24	4.3	b.Time spent together in play and fun, relaxation, mutual enjoyment	She has time for fun; good vibes; he is jolly; similar sense of humour; he is my favourite because of his fun side; because he is good fun he can make the training fun for me too; we can spend time together with cooking and I simply like her; she is great fun and I like to make rumours of other with her; she is very nice and the English lectures are enjoyable with her; he is great to study with and that's why I like his history lectures so much; she makes me happy; we play games together; we like to play together and drive the jeep.
			c.Sense of humour - Makes me laugh when I feel down	When I am sad, she can make me laugh; she can make a person laugh even if they are sad.
Similarity and sympathy/Shared interests/Trust	81	14.5	b.Their style of behaviour to me	Their way of talking and style of behaviour; their behaviour TO ME; he is responsible and eager to help; he is forgiving; peaceful; he treats me like his equal; she likes me as I am; understands me; he is straight in saying things; she is honest; normal; has sense of justice; I think she behaves like she still was 15 even though she is 30 now; she is older but behaves as much younger; she is close to our age
			a.Similar haracter	He has a similar personality; I think he is close and sympathetic and likes talking to people like me; we are very similar and share a similar worldview and perceive many things in similar way; his style is the same as I have; he usually has similar opinions; we share similar interests and character; we have lots in common and behave similarly
			b.Shared interests/Mutual sympathy	We share the same interest in our hobbies; we share music and singing; we both have music world; she has the same interests; we have similar interests; horse-riding; she plays the guitar beautifully and likes the same activities as I do; I like to play tennis with her; He also likes transport; he likes fishing; PC games playing; he is a lecturer of my favourite leisure-time group; she can do break dance.
			c.New skills learned	He showed me lots of tricks in breakdance; she can do different stuff with me (my hobbies); she helped me to improve my drawing skills
			c.I can trust them/Rely on them if something happens	Because I can trust them, and he helps me when I turn to him; I can tell her anything and she can help me with anything; I can rely on him; I can entrust thing to her; she understands me; if anything happens – I can turn to him or tell him with anything. I can trust her
Other answer	118	21.2	c.Material benefits I get	She is nice and gives us small gifts; she buys me expensive things; She works in KFC, and I have a discount there thanks to her; she always buys some sweets for me.
			b.My family	It is my brother; it is my sister, and she is very important for me because she is part of my family; my mummy.
			Other answer	Because she buys crap lipsticks in Teta...
IDK/No mentor/Invalid answer	172	30.9		
TOTAL	557	100		

Legend: Table 5 shows the favourite features of identified natural mentors, marked as a.; valued features of NMR interactions with mentors that youths appreciated, marked as b.; and features perceived as benefits of the enjoyable NMR experiences for young people, marked as c.

In summary, Table 5 shows the themes of the most enjoyable characteristics of mentors' personalities and mentoring experience identified and mentioned by young people. They appreciated mentors' supportive, caring, and empowering nature; inspiring characteristics and lifestyle; and sense of humour, interests, talents, and skills.

Interestingly, mentors' inspiring characteristics were perceived as different to youths' due to the distinction given by the age difference and related experience in mentors - something the youths perceived, and to which could aspire in the future. By contrast, perceived similarity in a sense of humour as well as similarity in characteristics and interests were distinguished as important, most enjoyable features where young people valued shared interests with their mentors. Young people described that mentors are close to them in shared interests despite the age difference. The shared interest over the enjoyable activity helped to overcome the age difference between the young person and the identified mentor. This feature, analysed as an age-factor of NMRs, with the linked perceived characteristics described in youths' mentoring experiences, is further discussed below as distinguishing NMRs from other youth–adult and youth–youth relationships.

One of the favourite benefits described in NMRs experiences was an experience of mentoring relationship as *a space for talking*. Related to the youths' perception of a *mentor who is interested in the young person and can actively listen to them*. Young people strongly appreciated the time they could spend together, because the mentors make time for youths as part of their interest and care of them. Within this time, young people emphasised the enjoyability of shared talks, the experience of NMRs as a space for talking and listening, and the perception of mentors' availability for talking when young people felt the need for it: 'She is willing to talk to me'; 'She is interested in me'; 'Always listens to me'; 'She is my favourite because I can talk to her.' Moreover, some of the young people felt they can *trust their identified mentors and even turn to them in case of need*: 'Because I can trust them and they help me when I ask them'; 'I can tell her anything, and she can help me with anything'; 'I can rely on him'; 'I can trust her things because I know she understands me.'

Besides the material benefits, *empowerment, and encouragement* in NMRs were emphasised by youths as another most likeable benefits they experienced in interactions with identified natural mentors (see Table 5): '[she is my favourite], she encourages me and tells me I can make it because I am well able to do it'; 'She helps me to fulfil my dreams.' Getting good advice from mentors when they turned to them was part of the perceived empowerment they received: 'He can always give me good advice.' The youths described the benefits of the inspiration and advice they got, perceiving mentors as their role models due to their lifestyle and wealth of experiences: 'He is wise, and he always gives me good advice for life'; 'He gives me good advice often'; 'He can be my role model.'

Finally, among the benefits of the perceived features of mentors and experiences NMRs, youths strongly emphasised the *shared enjoyment* in activities of common interest, and the sense of humour in the time spent together. Experiences of shared enjoyment further mediated intrinsic motivation (Ryan & Deci, 1985) with interest in the shared activity: 'He's good fun and makes the training enjoyable – that's why he's my favourite coach and mentor'; 'She is incredibly lovely, and I really enjoy English lessons with her'; 'I enjoy learning with him, and that's why I like the history lessons so much'; and related process of *learning*

the new skills and knowledge from mentors. As young people described new skills they learnt from the identified mentors: 'She helped me to improve my drawing skills'; 'He taught me lots of new tricks in breakdancing.' Finally, a shared sense of humour was also an instrument of coping with difficult or stressful situations that mentors use to support the young people in NMRs, and young people emphasised as appreciated.

Results 3: What are the perceived benefits of identified natural mentors as role models in youths' experiences?

The results in Table 5 show that the perceived characteristics of natural mentors can also be seen as the *benefits* of natural mentors for young people, in terms of the significance of these characteristics that youths see in mentors and can then try to mirror. To look at the identified beneficial roles of natural mentors more closely, the analysis of Table 6 shows that natural mentors function as role models for youths to identify with and to copy in aspects of their lives. Table 6 reports in what ways young people perceived their identified mentors as inspiring role models to copy in their behaviour, achievements, or lifestyle. Because of the age and experience difference, youths perceived not only skills and characteristics but also how these develop into master levels and achievements as mentors modelled this behaviour and its results for them. These characteristics distinguish identified natural mentors from other adults in youths' social networks. Thus, analysis of the youths' perceptions of mentors' characteristics that they see as inspiring or admirable can be seen as analysis of the benefits of mentors in one of their functions: as role models in different aspects of young people's lives.

Table 6 shows the detailed features of mentors that young people experienced and admired: Physical and sporting skills, and general skills that mentors have and youths admire, are traits that youths can copy and acquire via regular meetings with a mentor spent in an activity of common interest. Achievements in mentors' body control and their knowledge developed into wisdom are features connected to admired skills that mentors mastered and integrated at a higher level as observed by youths. As the descriptions show, youths have an opportunity to improve at these skills, as the youths observe and are aware of them. Youths also admired mentors' physical appearance, the risks of which we discuss below.

Another interesting finding in Table 6 is the importance of mentors' professional role in society for youths. Youths admired mentors' work ethic and habits, responsibility towards their work, and professional skills and achievements. As well as emphasising mentors' problem-solving skills, youths perceived these characteristics and behaviours of mentors as important to the extent that they would like to achieve them too.

Finally, in addition to features described in Table 4, young people particularly admired mentors' 'cool', 'calm', and 'independent' character and emphasised their patience, ability to tolerate things, and problem-solving skills. They emphasised their appreciation of mentors' optimistic, positive, and relaxed nature in their meetings. In contrast to the descriptions in Table 4, youths only rarely admired negative characteristics in their mentors under this questionnaire's item. Thus, we argue that although youths perceived negative characteristics, they didn't admire them to the level that they would like to acquire these in learning from mentors.

Table 6: Do you admire any qualities about your mentor that you would like to have as well? What are they?

<i>Most frequent categories</i>	No.	%	Subcategories	Content/Examples of description by youths
Sport/physical skills/Appearance	47	8.5	Appearance	Beard; beauty; his height; she is skinny; eyes and hair; I'd like to have her beauty; she has an amazing complexion; she has eight eyes
			Physical skills/Body control	Endurance: I admire what she can do with his body - tricks and dance steps; Yes, muscles; good fighting skills; flexibility, KUNG-FU CONTROL; Know how to breathe properly.
			Sport achievements	To be as good at skateboarding; riding a scooter, to win the Great Pardubice contest as many times as he does, training as good a horse and riding as well as she does; I'd like to ride as smoothly as she does; I'd like to play lacrosse the same way; that she can finish half Marathon...
Wisdom/Knowledge/General skills	33	6.0	Admired skills (to acquire)	to play games like him; playing the guitar; singing; how well he knows how to find food on sale; catching fish; picking mushrooms and how well he knows how to make fritters or fried food; she can speak Slovak; she can play the guitar beautifully, he's good with computers; being able to cook meat well; Knows about airplanes; works with camera; know music theory, and can play the piano so well; to play the guitar amazingly like him; he has good tips and tricks on drums; Grandpa always makes up good nursery rhymes and poems and all sorts of silly things; drawing skills; he can play 4 musical instruments
			Knowledge	an educated man who could speak four languages; I would like to be able to speak English that well; his knowledge of math.
			Wisdom	his wisdom (he always knows what to answer); her intelligence; I would like to be as smart as him; I really admire how smart he is; rationality; that he has such a good general overview; his experience.
Positive characteristics: Optimistic/Cool/Patient/Friendly/Caring/Efficient problem-solving skills	53	9.6	Positive and optimistic/Present/Relaxed	a positive outlook on life and enjoying every moment to the fullest; He sees something good in everything he does; I would like to be as cheerful and full of energy as him all the time; Being in such a positive mood and full of energy; Positive and creative; his optimism; his constant smile and joy; makes people happy; liking himself a lot; she has had many illnesses and still thrives.
			Cool/Calm/Independent/Confident/Grounded	not taking things personally; composure - how he doesn't show emotions; his calmness and composure in every situation; keeping a cool head in every situation; her confidence; His calm nature; probably being cool with everyone; their independence; honesty; probably be more confident and not so much to be attached to others; his courage;
			Kind/Friendly/Caring	his kindness; sweetness; able to forgive; s/he can always help ANYONE, even if it's not her favourite person she wouldn't let them down; he is kind, gentle and always there for those he loves; openness to other people; being friendly; perceptive; social
			Patience	Ability to withstand noise from small children; how tolerant he is with his kids; she tolerates almost everything well and cares for us; respect and understanding; listening; how she can help people
			Efficient problem-solving characteristics and skills	How she can handle my cousin; how willing he is to help; solves problems on his own; stays positive even in difficult situations; how he is able to pick up girls; the ability to communicate with people; hoe he manages everything; she has her own problems and she solves

				other people's problems; she doesn't have problems to talk to someone; he can give advice; he can say what he doesn't like; he's good at explaining things; he can also be strict when he needs to be.
Work ethic/Responsibility/Work skills/Professional achievements	13	2.4	n/a	Reliable; diligence and stamina at work; when he wants something he achieves it with hard work; learns fast; not lazy 😊; doesn't give up; to be as strong as he is; ambitious; conscientious; he's good at explaining things; he works; the authority he can deal with everything; Thinking clearly; I'd like to go into business (as he is); mad determination and talent; his devotion; punctuality; very professional in trading; architect; interrogation; she keeps everything organised
No	101	18.4	n/a	
IDK/Don't have a mentor/Invalid answer/Other answers	303	55,1		OTHER ANSWERS: I want to be older like her; she's of age; Progressive; giving them life; how he makes a living; he's been living in the woods for 15 years; she is a good boy; yeah he just does something he doesn't have to do; not being as stupid and funny as him; She has a lot of things; yes for example she can speak loudly; not swearing; having a girlfriend, going all out; BUT DALIBOR'S POWER IS NOT :); <i>mega stoner</i> ; Yes he can fit into the better class I can't
TOTAL	550	100		

Legend Table 6: Features that young people admire in identified natural mentors show how mentors' function in the role of 'the role model'.

Discussion

This study showed that young people (11–16 years, mean age 13.3) identified natural mentors most often (n = 105) among their peers or older friends. Their friends are the most important and common source of support, while their closest friends are identified as natural mentors. This finding contrasts with the traditional definition of natural mentoring as a relationship of youths with an older, wiser, more experienced adult. It supports the argument for revising the natural mentoring principles in youth–adult relationships that would conceptually clarify and complement the definition of natural youth mentoring (Van Dam et al., 2018).

Besides peers and older friends, youths mentioned and described grandparents, older siblings, family acquaintances, schoolteachers, youth-group and sport leaders, and one-to-one music teachers as natural mentors. In contrast to the literature (Van Dam et al., 2018; Zimmerman, 2002), they did not identify neighbours or church leaders. The lack of identified church leaders may be a consequence of the secular culture prevalent in the Czech Republic. Regarding neighbours as natural mentors, the parents of friends could be in a similar role. Several respondents described friends' parents as significant adults who provide supports in their lives. This finding is rare in the literature to date, and more in-depth exploration is needed in future studies.

Estimations of mentors' age is an interesting finding, as it differs with the age of the young people. Younger youths (11–12, 14–15 years) most often estimated the age of mentors at 31–50+ years – that is, significantly older than them. Youths who mentioned natural mentors in this age group often identified them among family members, such as grandparents. Significantly older mentors could also be identified among much older youth-work professionals in various institutions, programmes, and positions. By contrast, youths aged 13 and 16 most often identified natural mentors aged 15–26 – that is, older peers who were close to their own age. Not only do NMRs occur in youth networks as a form of youth–adult relationships, but mentors are important others who often recruit from the peer groups of youths aged 11–16. And despite the video stated explicitly that a natural mentor is *not* a parent, several young people identified their

parents as natural mentors. This study thus shows that for this age group, peer relationships are even more important than youth–adult relationships (except for relationships with parents). We can presume that parents are the most important adults especially for younger youths (11–13 years) while they expand and grow their significant relationships outside the family, first with peers and gradually with other adults external to close family bonds. Or, the bonding type of NMRs extends towards bridging natural mentoring (Gowdy et al., 2023). We can argue, however, that this study brings a new insight into perceptions of natural mentoring phenomena in the experiences of youths aged 11–16 that emphasise peer relationships and their importance over youth–adult relationships and turns the attention towards natural mentoring principles in the peer relationships. Nevertheless, the statistically-representative sample is needed to validate these findings in the future.

Finally, regarding the general characteristics of identified mentors, young people found them in congruence with the gender they themselves identified with. Previous research suggests that gender may play role in seeking natural mentors. For instance, according to Leck et al. (2009) exploring career natural mentoring, the decision to seek a mentor was influenced by similar factors for both men and women. However, with men more likely to seek a mentor when they value increased autonomy and hence indicating that gender differences may influence the reason for seeking mentors. Related finding of this study included youths of ‘other gender’, who similarly identified mentors in the same category in most cases, which is new data. On the contrary, Johnson et al. (2015) found that male sexual minority youth were more likely to seek female natural mentors than heterosexual male youth. The finding needs further investigation with the representative sample of youths in the future research study.

Overall, the analysis of young people’s perceptions of their favourite features in identified natural mentors and their experiences with them revealed several qualitative features in mentors’ characteristics, qualities of NMR interactions from youths’ perspectives, and perceived benefits of NMR experiences. We discuss these findings in detail below.

Characteristics of Identified Natural Mentors distinguished by Youths between 11-16 years.

Traditionally, youth mentors are described as adults who are significant for their provision of consistent emotional, informational, instrumental, and appraisal supports, companionship, guidance, encouragement, and care (Spencer, 2006; Greeson & Bowen, 2008). In this study, younger adolescents (11–16 years) refined the previous findings with youths’ descriptions of mentors’ characteristics in several categories, listing the general characteristics of mentors, and characteristics they valued or admired in experiences of relationships with them the most.

Firstly, youths most often described an identified mentor as ‘a good person’ with a caring, attentive, empathetic, nice, kind, and friendly nature who, as a result, is perceived as helpful and supportive. Young people also perceived mentors’ sense of humour and funny and witty nature. And emphasised their perception of a mentor as a clever, smart, and wise person in youths’ lives. Other mentors’ general characteristics were mentioned as responsible, reliable, hardworking, and talented, while a few noted their character as noble, courageous, honest, and with a sense of justice.

Following the general descriptions of mentors' personality, young people emphasised their features valued or admired the most. Here, mentors were valued as 'positive and optimistic', cool, patient, kind, friendly, caring, calm, independent, confident, and grounded. Youths also appreciated the perceived similarities in mentors' character for which they chose them, and admired mentors' problem-solving skills in different life situations, as well as respected mentors for their work ethic, responsibility/professional work skills, and professional achievements.

Features of Enjoyable Natural Mentoring Interactions and Benefits of Natural Mentoring Experiences Identified by Youths between 11-16 Years

This study also identified the qualities of NMR interactions: as features of care (mentors were perceived as caring; liking and having time for youths); fun factor (youths described feeling well and looking forward to their next meetings with mentors, enjoying time spent together in fun, relaxation, and play); and mutuality/similarity of shared interests and in mutual sympathy and understanding. Similar features have previously been identified, mostly in studies on formal youth-mentoring relationships (Spencer, 2006) but also in natural mentoring relationships (Liang et al., 2008; Munson & McMillen, 2008).

This study also links the distinguished, appreciated, and enjoyable features of regular natural mentoring interactions, with the perceived benefits of NMRs stemming from these. Previous studies found the main benefits of youth mentoring relationships from youths' perspective particularly in terms of social supports (Brady et al., 2012, 2017; Greeson & Bowen, 2008; Liang et al., 2008). This study shows more particular content with subtle features of mentoring benefits following the theoretical concept of social supports received in NMRs. Beneficial features are identified using the youths' authentic language when describing their experiences with identified natural mentors (see Tables 5 and 6). Thus, alongside the theory of perceived and received enactment social supports (Brady et al., 2017), the concepts of empowerment, encouragement, enjoyment, time spent together over common interest, perceived interest of mentor of a young person, space for talking, trust, perceived admirable characteristics and skills of a mentor, and received good advice – these all are identified as relevant benefits identified in youth-centred perspective in young people's NMR experiences, adding to the current discussion in the field and beyond.

Among the benefits, youths emphasised perceived support and empowerment, received in regular mentoring interactions as well as in the irregular life events in which they turned to their mentors. The benefits of received care were described in terms of the space that mentors created, and that young people could use for talking with them about their lives, significantly supported youths as significant perceived benefit of the NMR experiences in this study. The benefits of shared sense of humour were mentioned in descriptions of mentors who could make young people smile or laugh even in stressful events, and thus perceived as supportive. The benefits of mutuality, similarity, and shared experiences of fun over the mutually interesting activities were related to a described learning of new skills and knowledge, as well as to a sense of trust that some youths mentioned towards mentors.

Risks of Natural Mentors in a Function of Role Models

Youths also described natural mentors in negative characteristics that they admired and valued. For instance, they mentioned characteristics such as 'grumpy', 'stubborn', 'impulsive', 'angry', 'unpleasant', 'strict', 'moody', and 'silly'. The answers in the questionnaire also included 'steel' in a description of a mentor's characteristics.

Similarly to Deutsch et al. (2020) we argue that the characteristic features of youth mentoring grow and distinguish within regular and continuous youth–adult and youth–youth interactions that are perceived as enjoyable, supportive, and perceived as beneficial for youths. Mentors show an example of advanced knowledge and skills and help to shape these in youths through the mentoring relationship. In this sense, young people acquire the experience of mentors’ behaviour in interactions with them and advance their skills – that can also be maladaptive. Thus, even the older and more experienced important others who show youths socially undesirable skills and social roles function as role models for youths. The processes of natural youth mentoring and its benefits occur in the positive as well as in maladaptive youth-mentor interactions. In other words, the normative quality of the skills acquired in mentoring interactions – that is, the interpretation in mainstream society of the desirability of these transferred and learnt skills – can vary between desirable to undesirable. The mentoring principle of the relationship, and its process of learning via the close trusted connection, remains and can be equally enjoyable and perceived as beneficial for youths regardless of the normative quality of what is learned. Thus, as a youth mentoring relationship grows, the same relational qualities, enjoyment, and perceived benefits can develop between the young person and a mentor with socially negative or risk features. Mentors’ strong potential to function as a role model can present risks for youths. Though the prevalence of these features was not high in youths’ answers in this study, this finding might navigate the discussion on the risks of natural mentoring relationships, and their potential mitigation in using NMRs for youth support in formal youth-mentoring interventions.

Conclusions and recommendations

This study shows that, in their perceptions and experiences of natural mentors, young people strongly identified them as role models, whose different perceived experiences and strong personality features they admire. Literature in the field is still scarce on the role and function of natural mentors as role models. The field of youth mentoring is currently adopting a youth-centred perspective, articulating, and exploring youth mentoring as a type of social relationship in sociological terms of youths’ daily experiences and perceptions rather than in measures of health and well-being outcomes.

The current youth-centred perspectives emphasise youths’ experience and perception address gaps in the role of youths’ experiences and active agency in learning occurring within youth–adult relationships, while criticising heavily traditional developmental psychological theories on cognitive development (James & Prout, 1997). Nevertheless, the natural mentoring theory has not yet been explored in links to literature on youth–adult and intergenerational relationships with a focus on youths’ experiences, perceptions, positionality, and perceived benefits, currently researched and theorised in the field of childhood studies. Traditional theories on cognitive development in social context (Vygotsky, 1976) and learning by doing (Rogoff, 1990) that could potentially explain youth’s experiences of mentors as their role models, has not been discussed and potentially integrated systematically with the theory of youth mentoring to date. This study thus informs the field of youth mentoring in addressing its new youth-centred approach. While showing its potential in informing about the experiences, features, and perceived benefits perceived by young people as recipients of youth mentoring developed within daily youth-adult interactions. The discussion on how youths’ perceptions of natural mentors can be used in their daily lives, such as in institutions where youth–adult relationships are part of professionals’ job description, can thus follow the results of this paper.

To inform the emerging youth-centred mentoring perspective and active role of youths as mentees in research, theory, and practice of the field, it is therefore useful to return to the core of youth mentoring – NMRs seen as type of social relationship experienced in the general youth population of youths within their regular interactions with adults and peers in the social networks – and to explore these with a youth-centred focus. It is thus innovative and important that more in-depth primary and statistically-representative research be conducted on youth mentoring as a naturally occurring social relationship in regular youth–adult interactions, with focus on its functions and benefits, conducted from youth-centred perspectives while considering youths’ active role, in the E.U. context. To clarify function of a role model of mentors in youths’ lives and its perceived experiences, processes, and benefits, and other processes, functions, and benefits of natural mentoring in youths’ daily live experiences. Detailed knowledge of natural mentoring as a type of social relationship, and young people’s experiences and perceptions of it, is necessary to develop new mentoring approaches that better suit the current generations of youths in EU countries.

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Supplemental materials

Supplement 1: Research Ethics Committee, Faculty of Humanities, Charles University: Ethical research approval certificate.

Supplement 2: Table 1: Sample of participating schools and pupils in questionnaires

Supplement 3: Table 2: Gender and Age of questionnaire participants in all schools Supplement

4: Table 3: Place of living reported by questionnaire participants.

Supplement 5: Results table 4a: Socio-economic status of research participants according to education and employment of mother; : Results table 4b: Socio-economic status of research participants according to education and employment of father

Supplement 6: Questionnaire items

Supplement 7: Results Table 5: After watching the animated video: Do you think you can identify someone who could be your natural mentor – an adult who is somehow important to you except your parents – and describe them?

Supplement 8: Informant consent for young people, in the original Czech language

Supplement 9: Informant consent for parents, in the original Czech language

Supplement 1: Research Ethics Committee, Faculty of Humanities, Charles University: Ethical research approval certificate.

FACULTY
OF HUMANITIES
Charles University

File number.: UKFHS/78360/2022

Assessment Number: 032022/Kli

Assessment by the Research Ethics Committee, Faculty of Humanities, Charles University, Prague, the Czech Republic on the Ethical approval for the project:

„H2020-MSCA-ST-IF-2020 no. 101027291 ENCOUNTER: Experiences of Youth in Natural Mentoring Relationships“

Principal investigator: Tereza Javornicky Brumovska, PhD. , Marie-Sklodowska Curie research fellow (2021-23) in project no. 101027291 ENCOUNTER.
Department: Dept. of Psychology and Life Sciences FHS UK

The project was reviewed and assessed by the REC FHS UK per rollam on 22nd February 2022.

Conclusion: The REC recommended ethical approval for implementing the above research project.

In Prague,
22. 02. 2022

Assessment board:
doc. PhDr. Iva Poláčková Šolcová, Ph.D.
Chair of the REC FHS UK

Members of the Research Ethics Committee
2022: Mgr. Jana Wohlmuth
Markupová, Ph.D.
Mgr. Martin Heřmanský,
Ph.D. Mgr. Bohuslav Kuřík, Ph.D. MUDr. Anetta
Jedličková, Ph.D.

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Faculty of Humanities, Charles University, Pátkova 2137/5, 182 00 Praha 8 Czech Republic

Supplement 2: Table 1: Sample of participating schools and pupils in questionnaires

School no.	Location	No. of participating youths in school
School 1	Prague suburb	15 (Pilot questionnaire)
School 2	Prague suburb	64
School 3	Prague city	83
School 4	Region of North Bohemia, rural, socio-economically disadvantaged region	33
School 5	Prague city	130
School 6	Prague suburb	104
School 7	Prague suburb	104

Supplement 3 : Table 2: Gender and Age of questionnaire participants in all schools

	Gender of partici			TOTAL	
	Boys	Girls	Other gender		
Age of participants	11	19	19	3	41
	12	51	61	9	121
	13	68	46	10	124
	14	61	49	12	122
	15	46	46	9	101
	16	9	3	12	24
TOTAL		254	224	55	533

Supplement 4: Table 3.: Place of living reported by participants.

	No. of answers
City	369
City suburb	41
Small town	24
Village	33
IDK	66
TOTAL	533

Supplement 5: Table 4a: Socio-economic status of research participants according to education of the mother with place of living

		City	City suburb	Small town	Countryside	IDK	TOTAL
Education of mother/Female carer	Elementary schools	20	2	1	2	10	35
	Secondary school with certification	28	5	11	7	0	51
	High school with leaving exam	100	7	9	7	0	123
	Third-level education	128	19	1	6	7	161
	I don't know	93	8	2	11	49	163
TOTAL		369	41	24	33	66	533

Table 4b: Socio-economic status of research participants according to education of father with place of living

		City	City suburb	Small town	Countryside	IDK	TOTAL
Education of father/Male carer	Elementary school	22	3	2	1	6	34
	Secondary school with certification	31	4	5	5	2	47
	High school with leaving exam	95	12	10	8	1	126
	Third-level education	119	11	0	8	9	147
	I don't know	102	11	7	11	48	179
TOTAL		369	41	24	33	66	533

Supplement 6: Questionnaire design with questions marked in link to the analysis of the presented paper

Legend: The supplement lists the questionnaire items. Items marked in bolt concern to the items analysed in the presented article. Closed-ended questions concern to youths' socio-economic background (n=29). The open-ended questions (n=31) concern the youths' perceptions of the identified natural mentors and their experiences with them.

About your details

1. Gender
2. Age
3. Grade
4. School

About your natural mentor and their characteristics

5. Do you have an adult who you like/is important in your life who you could describe?
6. Could you describe an older/more experienced person in your life?
7. After seeing the short video, do you think you have a Mentor in your life who you could describe?
8. Is your mentor a man/woman/other gender?
9. How old is your mentor (approximately)
10. What do they like to do?
11. What they don't like to do?
12. What is their job/occupation?
13. What do they like to do in their pass time?
14. How are they as a person (characteristics)?
15. What do you like about them?
16. How is your mentor important for you?

About your natural mentor and you

17. Where/How did you meet your mentor?
18. How long do you know them?
19. How do you spend your time together?
20. How often do you spend time together?
21. What do you like the most to do together with your mentor?
22. Have you learnt something new/interesting from your mentor? What?
23. Is there any difference between your mentor and other adults? What difference?
24. Do you admire any qualities about your mentor that you would like to have as well? What are they?

25. Do they help you somehow? How?
26. Can you rely on your mentor? Can you give an example of when you relied on your mentor, which worked well?
27. If you could ask your mentor any question – What would that be?
28. Do you look forward to the meeting with your mentor? Why?

Last meeting with your mentor: Can you tell me more about your last meeting with your mentor?

29. When was it?
30. Where did you meet up?
31. What did you do?
32. How did you feel after this meeting?
33. Would you miss your mentor? Why?

Other important people in your life

34. There is an older and more experienced person (other than my parents) in my life that I like to see regularly.
35. There is an older and more experienced person in my life (other than my parents) who supports me in what I like to do.
36. I have a more experienced person (other than my parents) with whom I can share my joy.
37. I have an older and more experienced person (other than a parent) who cares about my feelings.
38. I have a more experienced person in my life (other than my parents) who I can share my troubles/worries with who I can look up to for some reasons (other than parents)
39. I have a more experienced person in my life
40. What do you like to do in your pastimes?
41. Who do you like to spend your pastime with?

About you and your background

42. What do you usually do during your weekends?
43. What would you like to do as a job when you grow up?
44. Do you know anyone who already does this job?
45. Who is it? Where do you know them from? What do they do?
46. Do you have a favourite hero?
47. Who is it?
48. What do you like about them?
49. Do you live with your parents?

- 50. Do you have any siblings?
- 51. How many younger siblings?
- 52. How many brothers? 53. How many sisters?
- 54. Achieved education of your mum/female carer?
- 55. Achieved education of your dad/male carer?
- 56. What is the occupation of your mum?
- 57. What is the occupation of your dad?
- 58. Your mum works on (selection from P/T, F/T, at home)
- 59. Your dad works on (selection from P/T, F/T, at home)

Supplement 7. Table no. 5: After watching the animated video: Do you think you can identify someone who could be your natural mentor – an adult who is somehow important to you except your parents – and describe them?

Answers	Frequency	%
I completely agree	154	28.9
I somewhat agree	113	21.2
I don't know	122	22.9
I somewhat disagree	60	11.3
I completely disagree	84	15.8
Total	533	100

Legend: Table no. 5 in Supplement 6 shows that after seeing the youth-centred animated video that introduced the participants to the theme of natural mentors, 50.1 % of young respondents could identify an adult in their social relationships whom they could describe as their natural mentors.